

YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA YANGICHA TA'LIM!

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola Yangi O'zbekistonda yangicha ta'lim haqida bo'lib mavzu yuzasidan tadqiqotchi olimlarning fikr va mulohazalari chuqur o'rganib chiqildi. Bugungi kunda amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirishga, ziyoli ijtimoiy qatlam darajasini orttirishga, o'quvchilarni oliy ta'limga bo'lgan qamrovini oshirishga, yosh avlodga berilayotgan imkoniyatlardan to'laqonli foydalanish uchun xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Olimpiada, maktab ta'limi, ta'lim sifati, oliy ta'lim, xalq ta'limi, "Pedagogik ta'lim klasteri".

ABSTRACT

This article is about the new education in New Uzbekistan, and the opinions and comments of research scientists on the subject were studied in depth. The reforms implemented today serve to improve the education system, increase the level of the intellectual social stratum, increase students' access to higher education, and make full use of the opportunities given to the younger generation.

Key words: Olympics, school education, quality of education, higher education, public education, "Pedagogical education cluster".

Bugungi kunda Yangi O'zbekistonning barcha sohalarida ulkan o'zgarishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Shu qatorda ijtimoiy sohaning asosi hisoblangan ta'lim tizimida ham bir qator yuksalishlar kuzatilmoqda. Amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning avvalo maktab ta'limi va tarbiya sohasidan boshlanishi globallashuv jarayonida bolalar tarbiyasida eng asosiy bo'g'in hisoblangan maktab ta'lim tizimining jamiyatimiz hayotidagi o'rni va ahamiyati beqiyosligini nazarda tutadi. Maktab ta'limini tubdan yaxshilash va ta'lim sifatini oshirish, o'quvchilarga munosib sharoit yaratish borasidagi islohotlar jadal davom etmoqda.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA

Ta'lim sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning asosiy qismini, albatta, oliy ta'lim tizimidagi islohotlar tashkil etadi.

Xususan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 - yilgacha rivojlantirish Konsepsiyasi mazkur sohadagi yangi islohotlar uchun debocha vazifasini bajarib beradi. Bundan tashqari konsepsiya mazmuni mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimini isloh qilishning ustuvor yo'nalishlarini aks ettiradi. Unda oliy

o'quv yurtlarida qamrov darajasini kengaytirish hamda ta'lim sifatini oshirish, raqamli texnologiyalar va ta'lim platformalarini joriy etish, yoshlarni ilmiy faoliyatga jalb qilish, innovatsion tuzilmalarni shakllantirish hamda boshqa ko'plab aniq yo'nalishlar belgilab berilgan. Bularning barchasi ta'lim jarayonini yangi sifat bosqichiga ko'tarish uchun xizmat qiladi. Ta'lim tizimidagi eng muhim yangiliklardan biri oliygohlar va ta'lim tizimining quyi bo'g'inlari o'rtasidagi uzviylikni, uzluksizlik va integrasiyani kuchaytirish bo'yicha pedagogik ta'lim innovatsion klasterini ishlab chiqilishi bugungi kunda o'zining ijobiy natijasini bermoqda. Ilmiy adabiyotlar asosida klaster tushunchasiga quyidagicha ta'rif berish mumkin: "Pedagogik ta'lim klasteri" muayyan geografik hududning raqobatbardosh pedagog kadrlarga bo'lgan ehtiyojlarini qondirish maqsadida bir-biri bilan uzviy aloqadagi teng huquqli alohida sub'ektlarning, texnologiyalarning va inson resurslarining integratsiyalashuvini kuchaytiruvchi mexanizm [2].

Ta'lim majmuasini tashkil qiluvchi bo'g'inlar o'rtasida mavjud tabiiy aloqani manfaatdorlik va samaradorlik nuqtai nazardan, ma'lum hududning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahvoli va ehtiyojlaridan kelib chiqqan holda ta'minlash tobora zaruratga aylanib bormoqda [3].

Yuqoridagi vazifalar ijrosini ta'minlash maqsadida Toshkent viloyati Chirchiq davlat pedagogika instituti bir qator loyihalarni amalga oshirib kelmoqda.

Jumladan: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020 - yil 12 -avgustdagi "Kimyo va biologiya yo'nalishlarida uzluksiz ta'lim sifatini va ilm-fan natijadorligini oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-4805-son qarori ijrosini ta'minlashga qaratilgan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirining 2021-yi 8-sentabrdagi 383-sonli buyrug'i ijrosini ta'minlash maqsadida joriy 2021-2022-yildan boshlab kimyo va biologiya yo'nalishlarida kadrlar tayyorlayotgan barcha oliy ta'lim muassasalari umumta'lim maktablari bitiruvchi sinflar o'quvchilari o'rtasida ko'p bosqichli (tuman, shahar-viloyat-oliy ta'lim muassasasi) kimyo va biologiya fani bo'yicha olimpiada o'tkazish va 1-, 2-, 3-o'rinlarni egallagan o'quvchilarni oliy ta'lim muassasasining mablag'lari hisobidan imtihonsiz o'qishga qabul qilish belgilangan [1].

Olimpiada O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirining 2021-yi 8-sentabrdagi 383-sonli buyrug'i ilovasi bilan tasdiqlangan nizom talablari asosida tashkil etildi hamda o'tkazildi. Olimpiada tashkiliy qo'mitasi hamda hakamlar hay'ati sifatida TVCHDPI Tabiiy fanlar fakulteti Biologiya hamda Genetika va evolyutsion biologiya kafedralarining tajribali professor-o'qituvchilari, jumladan b.f.d., dots. V.B.Fayziyev, b.f.d., prof. v.b. B.X.Amanov,

b.f.n., dots. L.N.Egamberdiyeva, b.f.f.d., dots. N.A. Mirzayeva, b.f.f.d., dots. X.A.Mo'minov, dots. A.Q.Bo'ronov, katta o'qituvchilar D.U.ZAkirov hamda X.S.Nurmetov, o'qituvchilar M.Asqarova, D.B.Saidova, Z.Sh.Sobirova, I.A.Allanazarova, tayanch doktorant N.M.Tursunova hamda D.N.Qarshiboyeva kabi kafedra magistrantlari jalb etildi. Olimpiadaning har bir bosqichi nizom talablari asosida beshta savoldan iborat bo'lgan birinchi tur, yozma ish (har bir savolga 10 balldan, jami 50 ball) hamda o'quvchilarda amaliy ko'nikmalarning shakllanganlik darajasini aniqlashqa qaratilgan ikkinchi, ya'ni amaliy ish bajarishdan iborat bo'lgan (bitta amaliy (yoki laboratoriya) 50 ball) ikkita turda o'tkazildi. Olimpiadaning birinchi ya'ni yozma ish bosqichiga uch soat, amaliy ish bajarish bosqichiga esa 2 soat vaqt berildi. Kuzatishlar shuni ko'rsatdiki olimpiada bosqichlari davomida o'quvchilar laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini bajarishda, genetika fanidan masala va mashqlar yechishda hamda biotexnologiya bobiga yuzasidan berilgan savollarga javob berishda bilim saviyasida bir qator bo'shliqlar borligi aniqlandi.

Olimpiadaga Toshkent viloyatining barcha tumanlaridan jami 63 nafar o'quvchilar qatnashib, o'zaro kuch sinashdi, bosqichlar uchun zarur bo'lgan savol va topshiriqlar fakultetning tajribali professor-o'qituvchilari tomonidan tillar (o'zbek va rus) kesimida tuzildi hamda ekspertizadan o'tkazilib foydalanildi. Jarayonning shaffofligini ta'minlash maqsadida shu kunning o'zida o'quvchilar ishlari tashkiliy qo'mita tomonidan shifrlanib hakamlar hay'atiga taqdim etildi, tekshirilgandan so'ng ikkita tur baholari umumlashtirilib, yuqori ball olgan o'quvchilar aniqlandi hamda bu bo'yicha qaydnomalar hamda zarur hujjatlar rasmiylashtirildi.

2022 yil 28 aprel kuni viloyatdan 10 nafar saralab olingan o'quvchilar so'nggi institut bosqichida o'zaro bahslashishdi. Olimpiadaning so'nggi bosqichida saralab olingan 3 nafar o'quvchi PQ-4805 qarori ijrosi asosida TVCHPDI ga talabalikka tavsiya qilindi.

XULOSA

Xulosa o'rnida aytish joizki, ayni paytda pedagogik ta'lim innovasion klasteri doirasida olib borilayotgan bunday islohotlar muhtaram Prezidentimiz qarorlarida belgilangan vazifalar ijrosini ta'minlashga, pedagogik ta'lim bo'g'inlari o'rtasida aloqadorlik, bog'liqlik va hamkorlik aloqalarini yaxshilashga, o'quvchilarni oliy ta'lim muassasalariga bo'lgan qamrovini oshirishga o'zining kamtarona hissasini qo'shadi deb o'ylaymiz.

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